

The symbolic tools of the Apprentice

Ferenc Sebök, PhD

Most Worshipful Master and my Brothers in your grades and qualities, this afternoon I will try to explain part I of the triptych of Lodge France n°9, East of Budapest, SGLH.

My presentation will not be exhaustive this afternoon. I will try to present the apprentice's tools which seem important to me. Of course, the time for this presentation being limited, it is obvious that my work represents a beginning of construction that the apprentices will have to develop, thanks to their questions, their desire to make progress in Freemasonry, to improve at various levels, and sharpen their own understanding of what surrounds them.

My approach will therefore be “symbolist”, like breaking bread with a Brother, to share, taste, discover and move forward. This approach will allow me in a second phase to describe and explain the first part of the triptych that your Worshipful lodge has, that is to say the Apprentice's Table.

Looking at the tracing board of the first degree, we can see various fixed or mobile tools. Tools are found in the Lodge Table, but also in the Lodge, for example the symbolic materialization of the Sun, the Moon, the three Colonettes (Wisdom – Strength – Beauty), the Altar where we discover the Volume of the Sacred Law (Bible) on which there is a compass placed on the square.

There are also other elements in decorum: the raw stone, the cubic pointed stone, the Lake of Love, the candlesticks, the candles, the hangings, the use of symbolic colours, the mallet of each of the three actors directing the Lodge (Most Worshipful Master and the two Wardens), a fourth mallet often placed near the rough stone with a chisel, a starry vault enveloping the Lodge, etc.

The Tracing Board, representing the Temple of Solomon, surrounded by the three Colonettes, takes a central place in the Lodge and alone represents the source of inspiration and study of the Freemasons. The Lodge, sometimes called “Temple” by some Masons, is therefore a source of reflection and research for Masons.

This Temple is arranged in a unique way:

Outside is the square and in the Temple, the Brothers are seated on two columns (North and South). The seated Brothers can contemplate the Lodge Table discovered when the work is open. An often imposing door is closed to the West and guarded by a Brother (Tyler of the Lodge), a sword in his hand.

In the East is the stall of the Most Worshipful Master, seated in the Chair of Solomon), surrounded by the Brother Secretary and the Brother Speaker (Orator). Thanks to the three Brothers who lead the Lodge and these two Brothers, the Number Five is achieved, which means that five “enlighten the Lodge”. However, at least seven Brothers are required for the Lodge to be “Just and Perfect”, which makes the Opening of the Lodge possible.

Now let me introduce some important tools for the apprentice.

THE FREEMASON'S APPRENTICE'S MALLET

A legacy of builders and stonemasons, the common mallet or hammer is used to break the corners of rough stones in order to adapt them for the use of builders. It represents the strength of awareness, the will in work. It reminds the apprentice Freemason of the constant need to rid himself of the superficialities and vices of life... Make progress in Freemasonry.

Freemasons are moral builders whose goal is spiritual construction. It is through the active use of the mallet that the Freemason continues to bring about positive changes within himself. The heart and mind can conceive, but it is in vain if the hand is not quick to execute.

The mallet (two-headed hammer) is also the symbol of the authority available to the Worshipful Master of the lodge, as well as the supervisors.

The twenty-four-inch ruler for measuring

Builders used it to measure and spread out their work; the 24-division ruler, or 24-inch gauge, represents the 24 hours of the day. We all know the expression: "make three 8s".

The masons' time was divided into three periods:

- eight hours of work
- eight hours to serve God or other men
- eight hours of rest

This reminds the apprentice Freemason that he is mortal, because his time is divided into years, months, days, hours and therefore not infinity which belongs to God.

The ultimate goal in our life is therefore to conquer our passions and make progress in Freemasonry ; therefore, become better.

THE CHISEL OF THE FREEMASON'S APPRENTICE

The chisel is also one of the work tools of the apprentice grade. The chisel is harder than the stone to square the rough stone.

The chisel also symbolizes education and learning aimed at gradually accessing knowledge, what the Kabbalists call "Da'at" in the Sephirotic tree.

It allows the mason more precision and to remove pieces and imperfections to evolve towards a cubic stone which, using the lever, can later be inserted into the construction of the building.

The chisel complements the mallet by reinforcing its symbolism. It clearly shows that all strength is in vain if it is not used wisely.

What is the building? For the irregular mason, it is about man and glory to man. For the regular mason, it is about building the edifice to the glory of the Divine, to the extent that, created in the image of God, we try to improve ourselves.

This personal improvement would be limited to the mason if there is not a desire to promote this search for self-improvement; in fact, the mason must set an example and promote his improvement outside the Lodge.

How ? Through his actions, his example, his search for truth, his tolerance, his spirituality.

Or this ? In his family, simply around him!

But what are the conditions to shine?

To be honest, free, of good morals, on the one hand; on the other hand, follow the path of the sacred triangle:

Faith, Hope, Charity.

These three spiritualist, theological values also imply the fact of having to square one's stone (personal approach) and later, insert the cubic stone into the building that we are building together (collective approach).

Thus, the Lodge is a spiritual dynamic, where each mason must be able to count on his Brother and where all the masons of the Lodge work under the mallet of the Worshipful Master who is a Master like any other, but who was elected to work the Lodge, to the glory of the Great Architect of the Universe (GAOTU), from Noon to Midnight.

In this symbolism we can think of the energy of the Sun from sunrise until sunset, where the Moon will take over. Don't we say in the ritual that the Most Worshipful Master is held in the East to open the work on the quarry of the day?

As soon as the Sun sets (symbolically Midnight), the Most Worshipful Master closes the work and the Brothers who lodge it under the Law of Silence. The Law of Silence which means, among other things, that one must not reveal what the mason heard, said, touched (felt). The chisel is said to symbolize education.

The chisel helps to give shape and regularity to the stone, just as education gives shape and regularity to the character by cultivating ideas and polishing crude thoughts. It also shows the benefits of perseverance and discipline. In the work he carries out on himself, the Freemason strives to perfect himself and to bring to light his latent beauty.

The metaphor of the raw stone which becomes the cut stone then takes on its full meaning. As you will have understood, the symbolic tools of the apprentice Freemason are intended to help him work on himself.

He must seek his own value within himself by getting rid of his imperfections. The metaphor of the cut stone is perfectly suited to this work on oneself.

It is important to know the tools available to the apprentice to carry out this work on themselves. This is the ultimate goal of traditional Freemasonry. Understand their symbolic dimension and the references to which it refers.

Finally, what does “Practice symbolism” mean?

It is looking at what exists like a large painting (a painting by Loge for example), it is also “thinking the thought” that is to say, behind a first meaning, finding others, because the paths are multiple and the understanding is multiple...

Thanks to our cognitive abilities, we do metalinguistics. Beyond the exegetical approach, we must share our understanding for the collective enrichment of the Lodge. It is therefore also finding common ground, aiming for a common understanding, even if we think differently (acceptance of difference, which implies tolerance). Universally.

Thus our mouth, our organs of phonation, connected to our mind, allow us to explain, define, specify, summarize, understand and arrive at an appropriation of symbolic elements on a spiritual level.

In this exercise for example, the role and knowledge of the two Wardens are essential. But having vast knowledge is not enough to enrich the knowledge of others; in fact, we still need a quality, an additional art, which is the educational approach, to make accessible, intelligible what we want to transmit and help the Apprentices and the Followcrafts to progress.

Transmission is essential in masonry and is only valid if there is good teaching, because the symbolism is difficult to master. Indeed, the “symbol” is a whole bringing together several elements, so that its whole represents more than the sum of the parts.

We learn every day to use our symbolic tools as well as possible, in order to put order in our ideas, in our minds as eternal apprentices.

The new initiate learns that the Master of the lodge is the Most Venerable sitting in the East, that his insignia is the Square (Rectitude, the Search for Equality...combining the shape of the level and the perpendicular) , and that the tool of the Senior Warden is the LEVEL and that the Junior Warden carries a PERPENDICULAR.

On the altar, he will see with the SQUARE, the COMPASS, the MALLET of the Worshipful Master, a FLAMING SWORD, a THREE-BRANCHED TORCH and the BIBLE open to the PROLOGUE of JOHN, that the Bible is called the VOLUME OF THE SACRED LAW.

A remark concerning the COMPASS: “one of its branches being fixed, it forms a central point around which the other branch can, by varying its spacing, describe numberless circles, symbols of our Lodges and of the Masonry of the extent perhaps infinite.”

The Compass also symbolizes the accuracy and uprightness of our morals. Oswald Wirth says this: “the COMPASS symbolizes measurement in the search for truth”.

The MALLET, for its part, must be considered as the symbol of intelligence which acts and perseveres, which directs the thought and animates the meditation of those who, in the silence of their awareness, seek the truth.

THE FLAMING SWORD is of biblical essence (the angelic guardians of Eden).

At the Masonic level, one of the interpretations is to say that the flaming sword “represents the battles that the Mason must endure making virtue triumph”, to “drive hypocrisy and crime from our Temples”.

The THREE-BRANCHED CANDLE, for its part, symbolizes the three pillars of the Temple, the three fundamental elements of Masonic work: “Strength, Wisdom, Beauty”.

To understand what unites **LEVEL and PERPENDICULAR**, it is necessary to return to the sources of the Building Tradition. In ancient Egypt, the scale of the two tools was made of a stone in the shape of the hieroglyph of the heart.

In the famous scene of the weighing of the soul represented in the “vignettes” of the Book of the Dead, we see this heart of stone placed on one of the scales of judgement. On the other board, the feather of Maât, symbol of the **RULE**. For the deceased to be declared “just of voice”, the heart must be as light as the feather of the **RULE**.

The **LEVEL and PERPENDICULAR** scale measures the “rightness of heart” of the Brothers and their ability to translate the work plan into their work so that the building is correctly constructed.

Speaking of Maât, you will have understood that the painting that I am going to explain is part of the Sephirothic Tree present on the triptych.

One of the names of the Temple is precisely “the place of the heart”, and what could a Freemason accomplish without the intelligence of the heart?

The Egyptian name for the chisel is “love”, because it is what connects spirit to matter to bring forth life. Its sharp appearance evokes the Moon, a reflective and triggering power par excellence. Using the chisel it becomes possible to move from power to action, from potentiality to manifestation, to reveal the right form where the light shines.

The symbolism of the **CHISEL** emphasizes the important aspect of fraternal work. Brotherly love is the channel through which creative energy is expressed and carved in the stone to bring forth light and give life.

The sculptor's job is to make the stone “sing”. Besides, in ancient Egypt, weren't the craftsmen, the stonecutters, the builders called “those who give life?” »

The **CHISEL** represents the thought decided, the resolutions made, and the **MALLET** the will which puts them into execution.

In fact everything is a tool for the Apprentice, because his **SILENCE**, the number **THREE**, the **COLUMNS J and B**, the **THREE GREAT LIGHTS**, the **TRACING BOARD**, the **KNOTTED ROPE**, the **THREE WINDOWS** and everything within reach of his gaze, of his senses.

The Apprentice will discover many elements on the Lodge Table which he will have to study and understand, before becoming a Followcraft, especially :

Understanding of the roles of the different Officer of the Lodge

The steps and signs

The Windows

The sun and the moon

The Lake of Love, knotted rope

The roofer's sword

The raw stone

The tracing board

The 7 stars

The number 3

The mosaic paver

The 3 colonettes Wisdom, Strength, Beauty

Columns J and B of the Temple

The candles

Etc.

The Apprentice must present a Masonic work (French rite) before becoming a Followcraft (Ancient and accepted Scottish rite and French rite). Some Rites don't request a Masonic work.

The path is long for any apprentice to discover the path of symbolism, the multiple meaning of tools, as well as his personal perceptions. The secret in Freemasonry is the individual meaning of each initiation and each path of Brethren; the rest is to be found in books.

Every apprentice must try to appropriate the qualities that the path of symbolism offers them, to make progress at various levels affecting the intellect, the spiritual, but also the rediscovery of oneself, perhaps allowing one to begin to see things differently.

Thus Freemasonry is one of the possible paths of perceptual development, of what surrounds us, but also of what we are. Freemasonry therefore offers an individual, but also collective, path of research.

I know that the Worshipful Lodge France, n° 9 uses the French rite. In addition to the presentation of the first part of the Lodge triptych, it seemed interesting to me to show a Tracing board (first degree, Apprentice) of the ancient and accepted Scottish Rite.

Finally, I will also show you a caricature "But seven makes it right and perfect".

“Alpha & Omega” triptych from the Worshipful Lodge France, n°9, East of Budapest (HU). We can see the Sefirot in the Tracing Board, with in the centre, the Yod surrounded by an infinite time which does not stop.

Daât is located here. This triptych contains the three degrees of a Symbolic Lodge: Apprentice – Followcraft – Master Mason. The Symbolic Numbers refer to the age of the Brothers.

In Freemasonry, everything is a symbol and symbols have infinite facets of interpretation and understanding.

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Tracing board of the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite Apprentice , 2010.

A "Just and Perfect" Lodge, caricature, 2022.